

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ANYE****FIRST NAME: MURIEL NGUM****PROGRAM CODE: DIPH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software: MSWord 365 MSO on Windows 10)

Key concepts with page number in text

1. Writing a good academic essay (EUCLID 2021, 7-14)
2. American vs British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32)
3. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 34-39)
4. Punctuations (EUCLID 2021, 16-23)
5. Style guide (Austin 2007, 41-42)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING: INTRODUCTION

1) INTRODUCTION

When I decided to go back to school this year, my initial plan was to stop working so that I could dedicate more time to my studies. After reflecting and considering the current context in the African region, I decided to embark on both simultaneously. I had this experience before when I was doing my master's degree in public health; however, this time around, I am in a French-speaking country, and my preferred language for studies at this level is the English language. Then I got convinced to do my PhD online. I started to research and discuss with some friends and colleagues to help me decide where to do my PhD. Most of the fingers pointed towards EUCLID, so finally, I decided to enroll for a PhD at EUCLID not only considering it a prestigious university but also because it is on the UNESCO database.

When I gained admission to do a PhD in International Public Health, I thought to start straight away with courses related to the subject matter. Reading through the syllabus then, I noticed the very first course is International Academic Writing, with seven periods. Initially, I felt sad, thinking I do not need this course. When I started reading through the

course material, I found myself taking notes; there was a lot of material that I needed to retain. From this experience, no material is ever useless; even if it is on a subject matter, there is always something new to learn.

After reading through the study material and watching the videos in period one, I will focus my discussions in this response paper on five major concepts, which include writing a good academic essay, American vs British English, plagiarism, punctuation, and style guide.

2) WRITING A GOOD ACADEMIC ESSAY

a) Basics of essay writing

This first period explains what an academic essay is and clearly states the basics for writing a good essay. There will be no essay except if the writer does not start penning down his/her thoughts. While an early start is key, there is a need to have a question in mind which should be defined and analyzed all through the writing and editing stage. Having an essay draft plan at the beginning is also very important.

I would like to focus on academic essays as there are many types of essays. This type of essay seeks to provide answers to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence (EUCLID 2021, 7). As mentioned above, it is advised to start early to avoid and not procrastinate. With a question in mind, the writer should thoroughly research what is already existing in the topic. This phase calls for critical thinking and being creative to pick out what is needed and useful for the essay. Initially, the ideas will be disorganized, but the writer should be able to put it all together, and the ideas flow chronologically in the write-up.

b) Steps to follow when writing a good essay

When the basics, as mentioned above have been done, the next will be to organize the ideas in writing, producing a first draft that can be improved through editing and redrafting. While doing so, keep the structure of the essay in mind, which is an introduction, body, and conclusion. Usually, it is recommended to start with the body, then the introduction and conclusion of the essay (EUCLID 2021, 10). Referencing is something we want to take advantage of at this stage. It is vital to ensure authors are cited with due respect, using the referencing style recommended for the essay. At this stage, read the final draft of the essay to check for spelling and punctuation (EUCLID 2021, 11). I will invite one or two readers to read through and provide feedback. Areas of focus will be spelling checks, logical flow, and duplicated ideas. Then I will incorporate the feedback from the readers and seek clarification if some points are not clear. Finally, the essay is good to be submitted, keeping a final copy both in soft and hard copy.

c) Rule of thumbs for a paper writing

The first point which I believe is key is an early start. Knowing when the submission is due and planning backward prevents a rush. Writing an essay requires a lot of focus from the side of the writer, putting much attention on a particular thing. This gives room for the brain to think out of the box and in one direction. The ideas should be put down in writing clearly and not necessarily at the same time. An essay or paper might take weeks to be completed through a gradual writing process. If done all at the same time, it could lead to a rush, making the exercise long and boring. It is always good to take a break and continue when the ideas start flowing again with a fresh mind.

There are so many online articles through which other authors have expressed their views on thematic areas. It is always very interesting not only to read what the writer has gathered from other writers but also how creative he is in his arguments, sharing his thoughts which might not necessarily be aligned with that of all other authors on the same subject.

I cannot stop without mentioning the need to proofread the essay for editing and share it with others to get feedback. This will serve as a quality check at the final stage.

3) PLAGIARISM

The ability to quote sections of a write-up and give credit to the author reduces plagiarism. EUCLID (2021, 5) defines plagiarism as “using a source of information without giving credit to the author of the information”. It is ethically wrong to use words and not cite the source.

Personally, I take this seriously to the extent that even when using words that have been used often by other people, I mention their names. For example, my former boss will always say, “Work hard as if your destiny relies on your hands and pray hard as if it depends on God alone”. This was like our anthem, I decided to quote him each time I used that sentence to give credit to the source. To be able to avoid plagiarism, writers should cite the authors in their write-ups. This can either be done through intext, footnote, or in the reference section of the document, depending on which one is recommended for their essay.

This is so important that I applaud EUCLID 2021 writers for adding this at the very beginning. However, I would have recommended a walk-through of the Zotero app with new students to ensure they have properly installed and are able to use it.

4) PUNCTUATION

The use of conventional signs and spacing remains a big challenge not only to me but to most people as I can tell through my interaction with colleagues. A missing

punctuation sign could greatly change the meaning of a sentence. In my day-to-day activities, writing is one of the must-dos. For this reason, I find it important to know all punctuation marks and their usage, and to be able to differentiate between correct and incorrect punctuation is very important.

One of the signs I still struggle with and have been corrected several times by Grammarly is a comma (,). It is always very easy for me to forget to add a comma, as its absence does not necessarily change the meaning of a sentence. EUCLID (2021, 19) highlights different scenarios in which we can use a comma. What I have learned new is the use of ellipses (EUCLID 2021, 22) to show that a text is missing. Usually, I will use an ellipsis and surround it with spaces. Still wondering how Grammarly has never identified and corrected this punctuation error. However, since I now know, I will be able to correct it for myself and others.

With all the guidance given in this course pack and the notes I have taken, it will go a long way to improve my ability to punctuate well when writing. Others will benefit from me as well.

5) AMERICAN VS BRITISH ENGLISH

Throughout my education, I used British English from secondary school to the university. This is no longer the case in my job milieu, as I now interchange the two without even noticing. This I can say is due to interactions with a wider network of friends, and colleagues using the American English writing style. I admit it is difficult to make a difference and stick to one, especially when it comes to using words of the same meaning and pronunciation but with a different spelling.

Initially, I thought it was not a problem to use the two in one document. After going through this course, I will adopt using either English or American and not the two in one document.

6) STYLE GUIDE

A style guide is a means of documenting your approach as a writer to certain elements of writing style that need to be consistent (EUCLID 2021, 41). Irrespective of the purpose and type of writing the style should be consistent. This avoids having several different formats, layouts, structures, and fronts in the same document, which will not be attractive to a reader.

In some cases, the style guide is proposed to the writer, as is the case with response papers for EUCLID and the publishing of articles on some websites. If no tool is provided, the writer can either use standard styles or be creative and decide on what style to use. It is worth noting here that when dealing with a group of writers, it is important to share a style guide to ensure consistency in individual and group writeups.

7) CONCLUSION

This introductory session course pack for my PhD in International Public Health is super rich in terms of content. At this level in both my professional and career life, knowing how to write good academic essays is very important. Throughout this response paper, I have been challenged to write and read carefully within the lines, thanks to the frequent reminders and corrections I receive from Grammarly.

Truly learning never ends, and this is a good experience that I know I will carry along all through this journey with EUCLID and my entire life.

REFERENCES

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